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An Empirical Investigation of Brand Personality and Brand Image

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ABSTRACT

A brand serves as a differentiation factor between products and serves as a distinguishing marker. Furthermore, brands provide consumers with references to determine whether a product is a classy product or not, increasing consumer behavior to make purchasing decisions based on brand recognition. Whether a company produces goods or services, the success of a company cannot be separated from the importance of its brand that has been developed over time. A marketing manager's goal is to differentiate their products from the products of their competitors in order to gain market share by using product and brand-related factors. A marketing manager's primary objective in establishing differentiation in the market is to use brand personality, brand image, and brand loyalty as critical factors. As a result, this study examines the relationship between brand personality, brand image, and brand loyalty as it relates to purchasing intentions for branded FMCG products. In the study, 420 questionnaires were distributed to FMCG consumers in Madurai, Tamil Nadu, as a convenience sample. In the following phase, questionnaires were gathered and analyzed for outliers and incomplete questionnaires. Accordingly, we have identified 400 questionnaires that have been completely filled out. The purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between brand personality and brand image, as well as how they impact brand loyalty and purchase intentions by using structural equation modeling (SEM).

Keywords: Brand personality, Brand loyalty, Brand image, Fast moving consumer goods, Purchase Intention.

INTRODUCTION

The business world is now increasingly concerned with understanding the behaviour of individual consumers in order to gain valuable insight into how consumers perceive, feel, select, purchase, use, and dispose of their products. Customer perception and view play an important role in determining not only what and why customers buy, but also how they use the product and how they feel about it. A customer is placed in a difficult position throughout this process as they are continually exposed to an array of information and products available on the market, and their decision to purchase is influenced by numerous options and choices available. A brand is a tool used by consumers to simplify the lengthy buying process. It may be a name, a symbol, or a logo, or a combination of all these. Customer decisions can be simplified as a result of the use of brand equity elements. An important objective of this study is to examine how brand equity elements interact with one another and influence consumer purchase intentions. As a result of our evaluation, we have focused only on a few brand equity elements, including brand personality, brand image, and brand loyalty, in order to determine their influence on purchasing behavior. In the following chapter, the conceptual background of these factors is discussed in greater detail.

CONCEPTUAL BACKGROUND

BRAND PERSONALITY

(Aaker, 1997) It is a set of human characteristics that are assigned to a brand name that constitutes its brand personality. An effective brand increases its brand equity by having a set of characteristics that are consistent with the interests of certain consumer segments. In addition to its functional benefits, the personality of a brand is a qualitative value addition. It may take some time for a consumer to identify parts of their own personality with the brand personality if they become regular customers of the brand. Brand personalities can be categorized into five types with common characteristics they are Excitement, Sincerity, Ruggedness, Competence and Sophistication (Azoulay & Kapferer, 2003)

BRAND IMAGE

It is the brand image that represents the current opinions of customers about the brand. This image can be defined as an association between the brand and its target market. It represents what a brand currently stands for. It represents the consumer's perception of the brand. A brand image is a set of beliefs consumers hold concerning that brand, and it should be positive, unique and instantaneous. (Faircloth et al., 2001) Consumers not only purchase a product or service, but also a brand image associated with it. A brand image can be reinforced by using advertising, packaging, word-of-mouth publicity, and other promotional tools. In order to create a brand image, the product's character is developed and communicated in a way that differentiates it from its competitors in a unique manner. In consumers' minds, brand image has many associations with attributes, benefits, and attributes. The benefits associated with brand image include functional benefits, emotional benefits, and rational benefits. (Wijaya, 2013)

BRAND LOYALTY

It is important to note that brand loyalty differs from customer loyalty in the sense that it focuses on perception (image and experience) rather than price (prices and discounts). Customers who are loyal to a specific brand believe that they will receive a higher quality product and superior customer service than their competitors, regardless of their cost. (Fournier & Yao, 1997) While loyal customers make fewer total purchases, they tend to generate greater profits. The maintenance of brand loyalty can be relatively straightforward once it is established, provided the product quality and service levels are high. Therefore, brand loyalty is less expensive to maintain than customer loyalty, which requires continuous offering of low prices and frequent discounts in order to maintain the position of the best deal on the market. (Lau & Lee, 1999)

PURCHASE INTENTION

An individual's purchase intention can be defined as his or her willingness to purchase a certain product or service. An individual's purchase intention is a dependent variable that is influenced by a number of external and internal factors. Purchase intentions indicate a consumer's intention to purchase a particular product. Purchase intentions are an extremely important marketing metric. (Chang & Wildt, 1994) A marketing strategy based on consumers' intentions, purchasing intentions, or intentions of using a particular product or service that may or may not have been

explicitly mentioned by an organization or brand can be referred to as intent marketing. In order to accurately determine what type of content should be displayed in an advertisement based on the intent of a customer, marketing activities or promotions utilizing purchase intentions can be effective. Using intentions as a measure of consumers' knowledge levels, marketers can develop marketing campaigns based on this information. It is possible to create an integrated map of how to conduct an advertising campaign by analyzing the purchase intentions of a clientele base in order to create a plan that is integrated.(Bian & Forsythe, 2012)

LITERATURE REVIEW

(Lie et al., 2022)As a result of their study, brand personality significantly influences purchase intentions. In the long run, the unmistakable personality of a brand can be instrumental in increasing or maintaining business equity. As a result, a business's personality is a crucial factor in increasing and building positive customer perceptions. Ulos products have shown to have a strong personality character as a result of the competence aspect of the brand personality dimension. It is essential that brands be reliable in order to survive and compete in this area. Consumers view the product as a responsible product, a product that can be relied upon, and one that will thrive in the market.

(Oluwafunmilayo et al., n.d.)According to their study results, brand personality (sincerity, ruggedness, competence, excitement, and sophistication) correlated with purchase intention; however, only brand sincerity had an independent influence on purchase intention. Therefore, Shop-rite bread producers will have a consistent purchase intention if they are sincere and consistent in their product quality and quantity. Moreover, the sincerity of the product will encourage marketers to market it more easily, since the product has already gained the trust of the public. Shop-rite bread producers will be able to increase sales consistently if they can be sincere with their product, which in turn will guarantee purchase intention. According to the report, self-esteem does not significantly influence purchase intentions. Shoprite is a market that caters to people of all social classes. In addition to being accessible to the rich and poor, Shop-rite bread is a more affordable and convenient product. Moreover, since Shop-rite does not impose any restrictions on purchase of items, consumers do not need to be self-confident in order to enter Shop-rite or purchase Shop-rite bread.

(Munasinghe, 2018)As a result, they concluded that promotional messages that include personality-associated traits are effective in influencing consumers to make preferences for personal care

products. As a consequence, the preference may vary depending on the brand's associated personality dimensions.

(Vahdaei & Nejad, 2016) Their study suggests that brand personality has both a direct and indirect impact on customer purchase intentions, demonstrating that brand personality has a positive and significant effect on brand equity. In other words, brand equity is a positive medium that can positively affect the impact of brand personality on customers' purchase intentions. Consequently, developing a positive brand personality based on the minds of customers can increase the customers' intention to use the brand and subsequently achieve a strong predictor of customer behavior. Considering brand equity as a mediator variable in the relationship between e-WOM and purchase intention can enhance the impact of this variable. Customers' online recommendations and offers to a brand create a positive image of the brand, which further enhances trust and loyalty among customers, which in turn enhances the customer's attitude and intention to use the brand.

(Dirgantari et al., 2021) In their study, it has been demonstrated that the transactional intention dimension plays an important role in creating a purchase intention. According to previous research, the consumer's interest or desire to purchase varies from consumer to consumer, and prospective buyers choose products based on their experiences and stimuli. However, of the overall purchase intentions indicator, the desire to buy Revlon lipstick is the one that received the highest rating. However, the indicator with the lowest score was more concerned with Revlon lipstick's physical form. As previously explained, consumer satisfaction is defined as how customers evaluate a product after using it, as well as how consumers compare it to other products in the same industry.

(Toldos-Romero & Orozco-Gómez, 2015) Based on their study results, it has been demonstrated that hipness/vivacity, success, sincerity, and sophistication are significant predictors of purchase intention. A negative correlation can also be observed between Domesticity/Emotionality and Professionalism which also explain purchase intention. Results are also broken down into product categories. Users of the brands are more likely to rate them higher than non-users in each of the brand personality dimensions.

(Othman & Rahman, 2014) They concluded from their study that three of the factors, sincerity, competence and sophistication, were significantly associated with organic fast food purchase intentions normally. Therefore, the outcome suggests that sincerity is the strongest ingredient in this relationship. As a result, the researchers concluded that fast food operators may be able to successfully incorporate brand personality variables such as sincerity, competence, and sophistication to influence the formation of customer intentions toward organic fast food. In this way, this study has successfully developed a theoretical and pragmatic framework for understanding Malaysian consumers' purchase intentions for organic fast food.

(Zhihan et al., 2022) As a result of evaluating and improving previous research, they determined that brand leadership influences customers' purchase intentions via brand trust and how those behaviors interact and influence customers. Consumer behavior, expectations, and attitudes correlate with purchase intent. In order to evaluate and evaluate a product, customers' purchasing behaviors play a crucial role. Demand as well as perceived quality and worth may influence the buying choice. In order for consumers' purchasing intent to increase, brands must be able to shape brand leadership and capture consumers' attention to enhance brand trust. Brand Leadership is an important factor in enhancing consumer purchase intent. By developing distinct feelings and relationships with consumers, brand leadership may improve the brand's perception in their hearts and boost brand trust. Finally, the brand's market leadership may increase. It is possible to determine the most appropriate brand management and communication tactics for achieving the brand development's strategic objectives by examining brand leadership's driving reasons and result-oriented approach

(Hakkak et al., 2015) According to their findings, brand personality has a significant and positive impact on brand equity and purchase intention. Also, the results indicated that brand equity positively influences customers' purchase intentions, as well as acting as a positive mediator between the other two variables. It is recommended that organizations and marketing managers take steps to establish a positive brand personality in order to differentiate themselves in their customers' minds from other brands, enhance their brand equity, and achieve a comprehensive understanding of consumer behavior as a result of the results of this study.

(Naresh Babu&Lavanyalatha, 2018)In their research, they concluded that brand personality, which is characterized by sincerity, excitement, and competence, is a mediator between celebrity endorsements and purchase intentions. Additionally, the study concluded that celebrities' endorsements resulted in positive perceptions of the products' value, quality, and knowledge.

(Mamangkey et al., 2017)Their research has revealed that Nike's brand personality influences customers' purchase intentions in a positive manner; this translates into an increase in consumers' purchase intentions when the product's brand personality is positive. Additionally, the results indicate that competence and sincerity are the most important factors influencing consumer purchase intentions for Nike sportswear products. Competence and sincerity have the highest factor loading on Nike consumers' purchase intentions according to the results of the dimensions of brand personality. In other words, consumers trust the brand, regard it as successful, and have a close emotional connection with the brand.

(Keni et al., 2022)As a result of their analysis, they concluded that luxury brand perception contributes the most to purchase intention, followed by brand personality and social influence. Hence, luxury brand perception plays a significant role on predicting purchase intention. In Jakarta, smartphone users were found to positively predict purchase intentions based on luxury brand perception, social influence, and brand personality. It is believed that consumers will be able to demonstrate their wealth and value through the use of smartphones. When consumers are continually interacting with family and friends, the influence on their minds and actions will be high. A smartphone brand's characteristics will be the way it distinguishes itself from other brands. As a result, these characteristics become the characteristics of its users.

(Tsabitah&Anggraeni, 2021)According to their research, consumers often hear the “This Is April” brand as a fashion product. This brand offers consumers an alternative choice. While “This Is April” is not always the brand of choice for fashion products, consumers are aware that there is a “This Is April” brand that is an alternative option. Moreover, This Is April's products also have features that can easily be remembered by consumers, such as neutral colors and apparel models that are simple but also suitable for formal events. As a result, brand awareness can influence purchase intentions.

(Malodia et al., 2017)In their study, it was found that the congruence of celebrity and brand personality positively impacted brand recall, brand associations, and reinforced brand identity. Attitude toward the advertisement and brand has positively impacted purchase intention. Attitude

toward the brand has positively affected purchase intention. A brand association and brand personality reinforcement were found to moderate the influence of brand identity self-image congruence and involvement level with the brand on attitude toward advertisements and the brand itself.

(Rup et al., 2021) In accordance with their study, the brand personalities of cell phone brands gradually create a brand attitude in the customers' minds regardless of the need, eagerness and economic capability of the customer to purchase the same product. As a result of this brand attitude, consumers become eager and likely to purchase the same brand when need arises, while reducing their preferences for other brands' products. As a result of a more positive brand attitude, consumers may even desire that brand, which can then result in the purchase of the same brand's products. Therefore, rather than predicting BPI directly, brand personalities induce BPI by establishing a consistent and persistent brand attitude in the minds of buyers.

(Lee et al., 2020) According to their study, brand personality, brand engagement, and purchase intention are interrelated, and whether self-esteem modifies the influence of brand personality on purchase intention through brand engagement. This study found that brand personality positively influenced brand engagement and purchase intention, and brand engagement positively influenced purchase intention. Based on their research, it has been revealed that psychological mechanisms contribute to the relationship between brand engagement and purchase intention depending on the level of self-esteem of the consumer.

(Mao et al., 2020) Their study findings indicated that flow experience, brand image, brand communication, brand personality, and brand identity all contribute directly or indirectly to purchase intention. An individual's flow experience mediates the path from brand communication to brand identity, personality, and purchase intention. This study examines the strategic implications of brand features management and strives to achieve sustainable economic, social, and environmental outcomes.

RESEARCH GAP

After reviewing the literature from previous studies, we have gained an understanding of the grey areas which need to be explored further. Their suggestion was to conduct a similar study with other brand-related variables, such as brand loyalty and brand image, in a different city or country. In the end, we came up with the idea of analysing the impact of brand personality and brand image on brand loyalty towards purchase intention.

METHODOLOGY

In order to collect data for this study, a questionnaire was developed based on literature that measures the following constructs: brand personality, brand image, brand loyalty, and purchase intention. In this questionnaire, the main objective is to assess the influence of brand personality and brand image on determinants of purchasing intention pertaining to branded FMCG products. Additionally, the questionnaire is divided into two sections, with the first including questions about demographic characteristics of respondents such as gender, age, marital status, education, and income. In the second part of the questionnaire, there is an evaluation question based on a five-point Likert scale regarding research constructs. Additionally, the research constructs have been categorized as follows: Brand personality – Sincerity, Sophistication, Excitement, Competence, brand image – Functional benefits, Emotional benefits, Rational benefits, Brand loyalty – Cognitive loyalty, Affective loyalty, Intentional loyalty, Action loyalty and Purchase intention – Subjective norm, Attitude, and Perceived value.

DATA ANALYSIS

DESCRIPTIVE RESULTS

According to Table 1, a general overview of the demographic characteristics of the respondents to the study is provided. Using the data contained in table 1 below, it is apparent that 52.5% of respondents belong to the female gender group and 47.5% belong to the male gender group. The majority of respondents are undergraduate students, with 46.3% belonging to the undergraduate group and 23.8% belonging to the postgraduate group. The following table indicates that 49% of respondents have family incomes between Rs.30,000 and Rs.60,000 per month, which is considered middle income.

Table 1*An Overview of the Demographic Profile of the Study, Sample (n = 400)*

Demographic characteristics		Frequency	Percentage %
Gender	Male	210	52.5%
	Female	190	47.5 %
Age	Up to 30	135	33.8 %
	31-40	97	24.3 %
	41-50	94	23.5 %
	Above 50	74	18.5 %
Educational qualification	Ph.D.	56	14.0 %
	Postgraduate	95	23.8 %
	Undergraduate	185	46.3 %
	Diploma	33	08.3 %
	ITI	16	04.0%
	HSC	05	01.3%
	Others	10	02.5%
Family income – monthly	Less than rs.10,000	24	06.0 %
	Rs.10,001 – Rs.30,000	112	28.0%
	Rs.30,001 – Rs.60,000	196	49.0 %
	More than 60,000	98	17.0 %
Marital status	Unmarried	101	25.2%
	Married	299	74.8%

Table 2

Confirmatory factor analysis : Calculation of AVE and CR For the Measurement Model

		Factor Loading	Item Reliability	Delta	AVE	Sum of FL	Sum of Delta	CR
BP4	<--- Brand Personality	0.832	0.692224	0.307776				
BP3	<--- Brand Personality	0.844	0.712336	0.287664				
BP2	<--- Brand Personality	0.826	0.682276	0.317724				
BP1	<--- Brand Personality	0.749	0.561001	0.438999	0.66195925	3.251	1.352163	0.887
BI3	<--- Brand Image	0.842	0.708964	0.291036				
BI2	<--- Brand Image	0.799	0.638401	0.361599				
BI1	<--- Brand Image	0.82	0.6724	0.3276	0.673255	2.461	0.980235	0.860
BL4	<--- Brand Loyalty	0.894	0.799236	0.200764				
BL3	<--- Brand Loyalty	0.762	0.580644	0.419356				
BL2	<--- Brand Loyalty	0.844	0.712336	0.287664				
BL1	<--- Brand Loyalty	0.582	0.338724	0.661276	0.607735	3.082	1.56906	0.858
PI3	<--- Purchase Intention	0.67	0.4489	0.5511				
PI2	<--- Purchase Intention	0.699	0.488601	0.511399				
PI1	<--- Purchase Intention	0.762	0.580644	0.419356	0.50604833	2.131	1.481855	0.753

The AVE should be 0.5 or higher in order to indicate adequate convergence validity. In general, a construct reliability estimate of 0.7 or greater indicates excellent construct validity. In the case of good construct validity, a construct reliability between 0.6 and 0.7 is considered acceptable. A high construct reliability indicates that internal consistency exists, which means that the measures are consistently representing the same thing within the model.

Table 3

Discriminant Validity of the CFA Models

	BRAND PERSONALITY	BRAND IMAGE	BRAND LOYALTY	PURCHASE INTENTION
BRAND PERSONALITY	0.814			
BRAND IMAGE	.197**	0.821		
BRAND LOYALTY	.533**	.220**	0.780	
PURCHASE INTENTION	.178**	0.012	.169**	0.711

According to **Fornell & Larcker (1981)** discriminant validity is determined by comparing the square root of each AVE in the diagonal with the correlation coefficients (off-diagonal) for each construct in the relevant rows and columns with respect to the above said rules. This measurement model provides acceptable discriminant validity, and it also supports discriminant validity between constructs.

STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODEL

Figure 1

Structural Equation Model

Table 4

Structural Equation Model Analysis

		Unstandardized Co-efficient	S.E.	Standardized Co-efficient	t.value	P Value
BRAND LOYALTY←	BRAND PERSONALITY	.553	.046	0.510	11.919	<0.01
BRAND LOYALTY←	BRAND IMAGE	.130	.047	0.120	2.796	<0.01
PURCHASE INTENTION←	BRAND LOYALTY	.122	.035	0.169	3.433	<0.01

As indicated in the above table, the Unstandardised coefficient of brand personality on brand loyalty is 0.553 indicating the partial influence of brand personality on brand loyalty when the other path

variables remain unchanged. As a result of the estimated positive sign, Brand loyalty would increase by 0.553 for every unit increase in Brand personality, and this coefficient value is significant at 1% level. According to the above table, the Unstandardised Coefficient of Brand Image on Brand Loyalty is 0.130, which indicates the partial impact of brand image on brand loyalty assuming the other variables are not changed. This coefficient value indicates that the effect is positive, resulting in an increase of 0.130 in brand loyalty for every unit increase in brand image, and this coefficient is significant at the level of 1%. The above table indicates that the Unstandardised coefficient of brand loyalty on purchase intention is 0.122, indicating that there is a partial impact of brand personality on purchase intention when all attributable variables remain the same. A positive estimate indicates that the effect is positive, resulting in an increase in purchase intention of 0.122 for every unit increase in brand loyalty, and this coefficient value is significant at 1%.

Table 4

Model Fit Summary of Structural Equation Model

Model	CMIN	CMIN/DF	GFI	AGFI	NFI	RMSEA
Brand personality & Brand Image Decision criteria	5.0147 P(0.08)	2.508	0.994	0.969	0.980	0.053
	P>0.05	CMIN/DF<5	GFI>0.9	AGFI >0.9	NFI> 0.9	RMSEA<0.06

The calculated P value is 0.08 as shown in the above table, which is greater than 0.05, indicating a perfect fit. Neither the Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) nor the Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI) values are greater than 0.9, indicating a satisfactory fit. As well, it has been found that the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) value is 0.053, a value less than 0.08 which indicates a perfect fit.

FINDINGS

This study examined the relationship between brand image and brand personality in terms of brand loyalty and purchase intentions. As a result of the results of this study, we are able to conclude that brand personality has a greater impact than brand image on brand loyalty. Furthermore, the study examined demographic characteristics related to consumer purchase intentions for fast-moving consumer goods that were branded. In this study, the findings indicate that brand loyalty influences purchase intentions.

DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

Among FMCG products, the greatest competitive advantage can be attributed to the high level of competition and enhanced growth potential, which makes FMCG products the most competitive in the retail sector. In order to overcome the tough competition among FMCG companies, FMCG companies must enhance brand loyalty and brand personality. Brand image is a key component of building a brand. In accordance with the results of this study, previous studies have confirmed the importance of brand loyalty and personalization. By creating emotional connections with the target market, a positive brand image and brand personality can improve brand loyalty. This may enhance the relationship between the brand and its customers, resulting in increased customer engagement.

LIMITATIONS

Despite the limitations of this study, future research can be enhanced by using a probability sample to increase the generalizability of our results. While this study has contributed significantly to the literature and practice, there are also some limitations associated with it. It is recommended that future research focus on industries such as clothing, dairy, etc., since this research may not be generalizable to all industries. Additionally, this study looked at the combined effect of different brand equity elements on purchase intention. Future research should examine other factors, such as brand association and brand trust, among others.

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